

THERMODYNAMIC MODELLING OF HP-HT KYANITE-BEARING MIGMATITIC PARAGNEISSES FROM THE ÓRDENES ALLOCHTHONOUS COMPLEX (NW IBERIAN MASSIF, SPAIN)

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Abstract

The Upper Units of the allochthonous complexes of NW Iberia represent a continental terrane involved in the late Paleozoic collision of Gondwana and Laurussia (Variscan Orogeny) that led to the formation of Pangea. This terrane bears the imprint of a (Cadomian) Cambrian magmatic arc located in the periphery of the West African Craton (Gondwana) and recorded Devonian high-pressure and high-temperature (HP-HT) metamorphism during the Variscan subduction/collision. In the eastern part of the Órdenes Complex, the HP-HT Upper Units crop out in the Sobrado antiform. They include ultramafic rocks, high-pressure mafic rocks (granulites and eclogites) and paragneisses. The paragneisses display pervasive migmatization, the leucosomes being oriented subparallel to the regional foliation. We conducted a petrologic study to constrain the PT conditions underwent by these metasediments and the tectonic evolution of these units. The mineral assemblage of these rocks is constituted by garnet-kyanite-biotite-plagioclase-K-feldspar-quartz, with rutile, hematite and apatite as accessory minerals. Pseudosection modelling in the NCKFMASHTO system reveals metamorphic peak conditions at 800-835 °C and 14-16 kbar, followed by a near-isothermal decompression ensued by moderate cooling. To assess the prograde path, a bulk-rock reintegration technique was performed in order to account for extraction of melt. Adding a 6% of an internally consistent granitic liquid to the measured bulk composition results in PT conditions of 550-650°C and 18-26 kbar for the relic mineral assemblages formed during the pre-metamorphic peak history. The PT evolution of the migmatitic paragneisses can be interpreted as the result of Devonian subduction (to at least 65 km deep) followed by a drastic decompression, during which the exhuming slab was significantly heated and mineral assemblages re-equilibrated under HP granulite facies conditions.

Key words: High-pressure granulite facies rocks, HP-HT Upper Units, Órdenes Complex (NW Iberian Massif, Variscan Orogen).